

Effect of Metacognitive Learning cycle model on achievement in mathematics concepts among secondary school students in Minna metropolis, Niger state

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Abstract

This study explored Effect of Metacognitive Learning cycle model on achievement in mathematics concepts among secondary school students in Minna metropolis, Niger state. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at alpha 0.5 level of significant. The study design was quasi-experimental with two groups: experimental and control group. Experimental group were exposed to metacognitive learning cycle model of instruction, while control group were taught with conventional teaching method. The population of the study consisted of 4345 (2216 male and 2129 female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) Mathematics students during the 2020/2021 academic session in Minna metropolis. Multi-stage sampling technique was use to select 96 (53 Male and 43 Female) students from target population. Three instruments were used for data collection: mathematics achievement test, lesson for based on metacognitive learning cycle model and lesson plan based on conventional teaching method. The Mathematics Achievement Test was validated by three experts. Test-retest was applied to establish reliability of the instrument, rating to be $r = 0.75$. The data collected were analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics. From the findings of this study, it can be concluded that exposing students to metacognitive learning cycle model has enhanced learning outcome in mathematics compared to conventional teaching method. The study therefore, recommends among others, that mathematics teachers should redesign their lesson models to accommodate metacognitive cycle learning model.

Keyword: Constructivism, Metacognitive learning, Metacognition, Conventional teaching Gender

Introduction

In primary school and secondary school levels in Nigeria, mathematics is taught as a core subject. Mathematics is the body of knowledge that open gate to mystery of science and engineering. Mathematics is pivotal to the development of science and technology of every nation (Unodiaku & Nwankpa, 2020). Mathematics can therefore be seen as a foundation of knowledge that contribute to scientific and technological development, and all-over human development. Its application to real-life situations transcends above profession to everyday life activities. Ahmad, et al. (2023) submitted that mathematics is the bedrock of science, and serves as a foundational component of engineering and technical graphics.

Despite the importance nature of mathematics and its vital role in senior secondary education in Nigeria, the learning outcome has continuously been poor for years. The external examination bodies results, like NECO, JAMB and WAEC reveal that only a little percentage of students that registered achieved credit-levels passes. Mathematics has been pre-requisites for admission into tertiary institutions in Nigeria. This consistently poor performance in subject has raised an alarm among mathematics educators and researchers (Zakariyya & Ahmad, 2021; Ahmad, et al., 2024).

Osuafor and Chikodili (2021) reported that teaching methods and strategies employed by many mathematics teachers in their classrooms as one of the major causes of underachievement in mathematics. In addition, the conventional mode of lesson delivering to learners was found not to produce the intended learning outcome. This mode of instructional delivering does not promote students' performance and it is teachers centered. It is only favour educational advantage students. The female students also complained that conventional mode does not fit their learning styles (Zakariyya, 2017). The metacognitive learning cycle model (MLCM) is one of the innovative instructional methods that have been recommended for use in mathematics classroom to address these challenges. To make sure that every learner in mathematics classroom is making sufficient progress in learning. The model of MLC is an innovative and modified instructional model that incorporates a clear pause known as check status into each of the phase models of the learning cycle (Elom & Aja, 2024).

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Metacognition referred to an individual learners' ability to plan, monitor, evaluate and make changes to their own learning behaviours in order to solve problem, especially mathematical problem effectively (Bitrus et al, 2020). It is sometimes defined as thinking about thinking, and seen as process of controlling ones' thinking about tasks, monitoring one's learning task. As a teacher in metacognitive classroom, you have an instructional role to play in creating metacognitive awareness. The teacher should provide an opportunity for students to ask themselves these questions such as: Have I done this before? How did I do it? What did I find easy? What was difficult? Why did I find it easy or difficult? What did I learn? What do I have to do to tackle this task? Should I use the same way as before?

According to Unodiaku & Nwankpa (2020) that metacognitive learning styles can provide the students with self-knowledge and make the learning process more efficient and effective. The learning styles need to be considered alongside the need to develop metacognitive awareness. It is worthy to mention that metacognition assists learners of all ages to transmit their knowledge and understanding across tasks and contexts, including reading comprehension, writing mathematics, reasoning and problem-solving. It has been found to be a strategy that improve the outcomes of disadvantaged students in mathematics classroom (Wonu & Nwoko, 2022). Achafust (2015) stressed that metacognitive awareness increases learners to learn independently, improved resilience, cost-effectiveness, emotional and social growth, and transferable knowledge. To Scholars, like Bitrus and Dashe (2020) submitted that metacognition is a self-monitory process that assists learners to gain orientation, which in turn resulted in academic success. A research evidences by Hessels and Schwab (2015) commented that there is a strong positive relationship between metacognitive thinking and mathematics achievement. This shows that metacognition plays a vital role in enhancing students' achievement in mathematics. Self-regulation can be described as learning that is guided by metacognition. Also, self-regulated students believe that opportunities exist to take challenging task, practices their learning, develop a deep understanding of subject matter, and exert some efforts that will give rise to achievement.

In metacognitive classroom, the teacher's duty is to prompt and facilitate thinking aloud. The teacher mainly direct on guided task that will lead the students to develop their own confidence and construct their own knowledge. Students are then equipped with skills in creative thinking and problem solving thereby enabling the students to assume responsibility for their learning. An intelligent learner thinks before he speaks or acts, therefore, thinking is a unique quality of a rational being. It is the power of an individual being, which went round the processes of recalling, retrieving, imagining, categorizing, analyzing, synthesizing, deducing and inferring (Elom & Aja, 2024). The development of the ability to think is a common objective of any educational task. It a common believes that thinking cannot be left from knowledge and knowledge involves the mind as a whole. Generally, thinking is one of many processes in which a learner does something internally to provide a solution to a problem.

The present study is adopting Metacognitive Learning Cycle Model (MLCM) developed by Blank (2000). The model makes sure every participant in the group make sufficient progress, and has four phases based on lesson presentation. These are: concept exploration, concept assessment, concept invention, and concept application. Details is presented in Figure below:

Phase 1: Concept Exploration (CE)- The teacher presents a task to the all class and provide a detail guide to the students to serve as an eye-opening for a variety of approaches. This provides an opportunity to retrieve and recall their previous knowledge for usage.

Phase 2: Concept Assessment (CA)- Here the students were asked to reflect on their mathematical ideas of the task before the instruction begins. The students will record down their thoughts/ideas, and reasons for such thoughts/ideas.

Phase 3: Concept Invention (CI)- At this phase, the teacher will note all information received from students' discrepancies at the exploration and introducing the main topic of the lesson. All instructional materials require for the lesson presentation must be provided and used to facilitate the concept invention (introduction). Such instructional materials like textbooks, audio-visual, concrete objects, etc., are then integrate in the lesson presentation.

Phase 4: Concept Application (CA)- This is the final phase; the students were given the opportunities to explore their merits and applications of the concepts. For each of phase the learners need to reflect on the learning status before moving to the next phase. Through this, learners are encouraging to keep a journal or note to record events at each learning phase, this then improves their understanding of the concept. Metacognitive learning cycle encourages critical thinking and reflective thinking, which promote learning outcome. This is achieved through frequent questions and providing enough support to allow learners to challenge their current conceptions of knowledge, and interaction with other peers (Osuafor & Chikodili, 2021). Learning outcome is sometimes known as academic achievement, it is the yardstick of attainment by students after being taught by teacher. This is usually being measured through homework, test and examination conducted by school and external examination bodies, like WAEC, NECO, JAMB. It is the degree for assessing students' success or failure upon learning objective, is typically assessed as either high or low corresponding to good or poor performance (Ahmad, et al., 2024). The assessment of academic achievement hinges on examinations, test or continuous assessment which may be influenced by gender.

Gender is a socio-cultural factor of ascribing some characters and roles to a particular sex-males and females. Influence of gender on students' learning comes in mathematics has been major concern of mathematics educators and researchers for long time but no consistent outcome has emerged. Scholars like Zakariyya and Ahmad (2021) found that there was significance difference in the academic achievement of male and female students due to instructional method used in delivering classroom lessons. Furthermore, Onyedike (2011) reported that male students demonstrated higher academic achievement than female students, suggesting that gender has major influence on students' learning outcome when exposed to metacognitive classroom setting. Okonkwo (2016) found that gender was not a significant factor in basic science and mathematics, and that it has no significant impact on students' academic performance when taught using metacognitive classroom environment. The study by Osuafor and Chikodili (2021) revealed that there is no significant interaction effect of instructional methods and gender on students' learning outcome in mathematics. The research report by Zakariyya (2017) showed that when male and female students were taught using metacognitive strategy, they performed equally the same.

Zakariyya (2017) and Osuafor and Chikodili (2021) reported that incorporate innovative mode of instruction such as metacognitive would improve students' understanding and consequently bring out the desired learning outcomes. The general public, including parents have been paying great attention to senior secondary school students' performance in mathematics as reported by WAEC Chief Examiner (2021 -2023). In light of the above, the study wishes to find out whether students exposed to metacognitive learning cycle model and those taught using conventional teaching method will be equal in their learning outcome.

Mathematics is the foundation knowledge of science and technology, without its knowledge scientific and technological development aimed in Nigeria cannot be realized. Mathematics provides students with creative reasoning and critical thinking to engage into different faces of problem-solving as well as prepares them to science discovery, analyses and interprets findings. However, students continue to record poor performance in both internal and external examinations as reported by WAEC (2020 & 2021). In both reports, the quadratic equation among others is one of the areas where students performed poorly. One of the contributors in students' poor performance was teacher's instructional strategy (Zakariyya, 2017). The studies of Osuafor and Chikodili (2021) and Parian, et al (2018) has shown the effectiveness of using metacognitive strategy to improve students' performance in mathematics and chemistry respectively. It was against this background that this study explore the effect of metacognitive learning cycle model on achievement in mathematics concepts among secondary school students in Minna metropolis, Niger state.

Objectives of the study

This study investigates whether metacognitive learning cycle model (MLCM) affected students' learning outcome in mathematics. The Objectives of the study were to ascertain:

1. Determine the effects of the metacognitive learning cycle model on students' learning outcome in mathematics.
2. Determine the effects of the metacognitive learning cycle model on male and female students' learning outcome in mathematics.

Research Questions

1. What are mean scores of students taught using metacognitive learning cycle model compare to those students taught mathematics using conventional teaching method?
2. What are the mean scores of male and female students taught using metacognitive learning cycle model?

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were tested with level of significance at 0.5 alpha.

1. H₀₁: There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of students exposed to mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Minna metropolis
2. H₀₂: There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model in Minna metropolis.

Methodology

This study adopted quasi-experimental research design that utilized intact classes that required no randomization of the subjects involved. The design consisted of pre-test, post-test, control, non-equivalent and non-randomization intact-class. The study comprises of two different groups: experimental and control group. Experimental group were instructed using lesson model designed on Metacognitive Learning Cycle Model, while control group were taught using lesson model based Conventional Teaching Method.

The target population of the study consisted of 4345 (2216 male and 2129 female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) Mathematics students during the 2020/2021 academic session in Minna metropolis. Multi-stage sampling technique was use to select 96 (53 Male and 43 Female) students from target population. The sample size of students was determine based on the central limit theory, which recommends an appropriate sample size of N=30 for research studies (Sambo, 2008). At first stage, a clustering sampling was employed to divide the schools into two clusters based on school locations. At second stage, simple random sampling was used by writing the name of the school in each cluster and picking one school in each cluster. At third stage, simple random sampling using flipping of coin to assign one school as experimental and the other as control. At the last stage simple random sampling was used by writing the letters of the arms and asking an independent person to pick one in each group. Thus, two intact-classes were selected from selected schools giving 47 students for experimental and 49 students for control. Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) for data collection was developed by researchers covering content areas during the treatment (solving quadratic equations, Pythagoras' theorem). MAT was validated by three experts from FUT Minna and IBBU Lapai. The reliability of the instrument was achieved through test-retest using PPMCC as r=0.75. The data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean score and mean differences was used to address research questions, while null hypotheses was tested at 0.5 level of significant using ANCOVA.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What are mean scores of students taught using metacognitive learning cycle model compare to those students taught mathematics using conventional teaching method?

Table 1: Achievement Scores in the Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain	Mean Differences
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
Metacognitive	47	40.48	9.42	51.69	1.45	11.21	9.69
Conventional	49	41.83	9.14	43.37	10.36	1.54	
Total	96						

The results obtained from Table 1 indicates that mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Metacognitive Learning Cycle Model(MLCM) are higher than those expose to Conventional Teaching Method(CTM) because the mean gain 11.21 for the experimental group is greater than 1.54 mean gain for the control group. The mean difference 9.67 favour's the experimental group, which address the first research question asked. However, to establish significant difference the corresponding null hypothesis was tested using ANCOVA.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of students exposed to mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Minna metropolis. The results in Table 2 shows the details:

Table2: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of mean achievement scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Sources of variance	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-CAL	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	27734.269 ^a	2	13867.135	1217.605	.000	
Intercept	3209.868	1	3209.868	281.843	.000	
PRETEST	13.744	1	13.744	1.207	.274	
GROUP	25497.058	1	25497.058	66.235	.000	S
Error	1560.274	93	11.389			
Total	477114.000	96				
Corrected Total	29294.543	97				

a. R Squared = .605 (Adjusted R Squared = .576)

Table 1 shows that $F(1, 93) = 66.235, P = .000$, this indicates that P-value is less than the alpha value of .05, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that MLCM is more effective.

Research Question 2: What are the mean scores of male and female students taught using metacognitive learning cycle model?

Table 3: Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain	Mean Differences
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Male	25	33.50	8.41	51.21	16.13	17.71	
Female	22	27.72	8.32	40.39	15.06	12.67	5.07
	47						

From Table 3 above, the pretest mean achievement scores and standard deviation were 33.50 and 8.41 for male students and 27.72 and 8.32 female students respectively. Similarly, the post test mean achievement scores and standard deviation were 51.21 and 16.13 for male students and 40.39 and 15.06 for female students. Apparently, there was reasonable mean difference of 5.04. To establish whether there is significant difference in the stated null hypothesis two Analysis of Covariance(ANCOVA) was utilized.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model in Minna metropolis. The Table 4 gives the details of result obtained from the analysis

Table4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) achievement scores male and female students in Experimental Group

Sources of variance	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-Cal	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	2768.059 ^a	2	1384.030	7.148	.001	
Intercept	13016.035	1	13016.035	67.223	.000	
PRETEST	2707.487	1	2707.487	13.983	.000	
GROUP	530.849	1	530.849	51.431	.000	S
Error	26526.483	44	193.624			
Total	477114.000	46				
Corrected Total	29294.543	47				

a. R Squared = .532 (Adjusted R Squared = .521)

Result in Table 2 shows that $F(1, 44) = 51.431$, $P\text{-value} = .00$ which means $P\text{-value}$ less than the alpha value of .05, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies there was significant difference between academic achievement of male and female students taught mathematics using MLCM.

Discussions of Findings

The findings of this study provide evidences confirming a statistical significant between students taught mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model and those exposed to conventional teaching method. This shows in the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental and control groups. It implies that metacognitive learning cycle model was more effective learning than conventional teaching method. This result is consistent with study conducted by Elom and Aja (2024). Osuofor and Chikodili, (2021) also confirmed this finding of this study by stressing that metacognitive learning cycle encourages critical thinking and reflective thinking, which promote learning outcome. This is achieved through frequent questions and providing enough support to allow learners to challenge their current conceptions of knowledge, and interaction with other peers. According to Bitrus and Dashe (2020) that metacognitive learning strategy is a self-monitory process that helps learners to gain orientation and learners' Centre which resulted to academic success. Furthermore, Hessels and Schwab (2015) discovered there is a strong positive association between metacognition thinking and mathematics achievement and that metacognition plays a vital role in enhancing students' achievement in mathematics.

Table 2 revealed that male students in experimental group had higher academic mean gain comparing to female students. The academic achievement of male and female students differs significantly in group. This present study is supported by research report of Ahmad and Aliyu (2023), they submitted that the academic achievement of male and female students differs significantly due to innovative teaching method. Zakariyya (2017) reported that male and female students performed equally when exposed to metacognitive strategy. Scholar like, Okonkwo (2016) found that gender was not a significant factor in basic science and mathematics, and that it has no significant impact on students' academic performance when taught using metacognitive classroom environment. Furthermore, Osuofor and Chikodili (2021) revealed that there is no significant interaction effect of instructional methods and gender on students' learning outcome in mathematics.

Conclusion

Considering the findings of this study, it was concluded that exposing students to metacognitive learning cycle model would enhancing learning outcome in mathematics comparing to conventional teaching method. Additionally, there was significant difference between male and female students when taught mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model. For the fact male students performed significantly better than female students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the followings recommendations were made, among others:

1. Mathematics teachers should incorporate metacognitive learning cycle in their instruction delivery in senior secondary school as alternative of conventional teaching mode.
2. Curriculum planners should plan to incorporate metacognitive learning cycle model as part of innovative instructional method in teaching-learning mathematics in secondary schools.
3. Mathematics teachers should train in using the model through workshops and conferences.

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